

Different Physical Information and Entropy Associated with Energy and Momentum?

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Classical mechanics defines the concepts of work = $\int dx F$ = change in kinetic energy and impulse = $\int dt F$ = change in momentum (vector). We argue that these two concepts are associated with different physical processes and contain different information. For example, a change in momentum is associated with an impulse e.g. the striking (and possibly breaking of a target) and there is a degeneracy in that $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$. Kinetic energy, on the other hand, describes a different physical process, namely the “climbing of a potential hill” and one may have different (m, v) sets yielding the same kinetic energy, just as the same p (same impulse) may be associated with different kinetic energies. Thus there are two distinct physical processes (impulse and interchange of kinetic energy or energy) and each of these are associated with different information.

In quantum mechanics, $\exp(-iEt)$ describes the time dependent part of a free particle wavefunction (spatial probability) while $\exp(ipx)$ describes spatial. We have argued in previous notes that this probability should be associated with entropy, but in that case there should be an entropy in time and one in space. Given that E and p differ numerically, one needs a reason for the existence of two different entropies. We argue that they are associated with different physical processes and information and so two different entropies may be possible. (We use nonrelativistic expressions here, but the same ideas apply to the special relativistic case.)

Work Versus Impulse

Classical mechanics defines two quantities which are associated with force F i.e

Impulse = $\int F dt$ = change in momentum vector ((1a))

Work = $\int F dx$ = change in kinetic energy ((1b))

Classical mechanics, however, is mostly concerned with $x(t)$ which is linked with the work picture because one knows velocity dx/dt . In the impulse picture, one does not need to know velocity i.e. $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$.

We argue that E and p describe different physical processes and have their own information. For example, the change in p represents an impulse which is associated with the striking (and possibly breaking) of a target. One may think of p reflecting as $-p$. In such a case, the degeneracy is $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$. One does not need to know m (mass) or v (velocity) to know momentum and its effect on a target. Furthermore, two m_1v_1, m_2v_2 such that $m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ have different kinetic energies. This means they reach different heights “climbing a potential hill”. They are the same for one kind of physical interaction (impulse), but different for another (kinetic energy to potential).

Similarly, kinetic energy has its own physical interaction picture, i.e. kinetic energy is converted into potential, as one example. There is also a degeneracy as different (m, v) sets may have the

same kinetic energy. Thus two particles with different p , and hence different impulse hits, may have the same kinetic energy and travel the same distance up the potential hill.

In short, kinetic energy and momentum seem to be associated with distinct physical interactions and contain their own degeneracies. As a result, in order to have full information about interactions, one needs both E and p which is the case for the special relativistic vector (p, E) .

The Quantum Situation

A quantum free particle is associated with the wavefunction (special two dimensional probability) $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. In the case of a photon, $E=pc$ and ct places time on the same footing as x . For a photon:

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) = \exp(-i p ct + i px) \quad ((2))$$

Thus if one uses the variables ct and x , a photon has the same frequency in ct and x space i.e. the same probability. If one uses probability to create a kind of entropy, say using probability = $C |\cos(p ct)|$ or $C^2 |\cos(px)|$, the photon has the same entropy in both ct and x space.

Such, however, is not the case for a particle with rest mass, but we argue that in the case of mass, kinetic energy and impulse hits are physically different. It seems that there may be a different entropy associated with $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ based on physical grounds and the idea that both represent different kinds of physical interactions.

In quantum mechanics, impulse hits exist just as in classical physics. We argue in fact, that they are the main form of interaction with a potential $V(x)$ or for a change in the index of refraction. For example, a photon moving in the x direction reflecting or refracting at $x=0$ from an interface $n_1=1$ versus $n_2>n_1$ along y undergoes impulse hits. In the region with index of refraction n_2 , the photon has momentum p_2 and velocity c_2 . Then $\exp(ip_2x)$ describes the spatial wavefunction while $\exp(i p_2 c_2t)$ describes the time one. In other words, x is considered to be the same in n_1 and n_2 , but time must be altered by multiplying it by an appropriate velocity in the new medium (i.e. n_2).

For particles with rest mass, we argue that impulses are means of interaction with a potential $V(x)$. This is why $\exp(ipx)$ is used in an ensemble, called the wavefunction, i.e.

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((3))$$

This might suggest that the kinetic energy type of interaction does not appear in quantum mechanics, but the fact that one has a potential energy $V(x)$ suggests otherwise. It seems that impulse hits must create an average kinetic energy (which requires the extra information of a rest mass). This average kinetic energy may be added to a potential energy $V(x)$ to yield a constant average E_n i.e. the time-independent Schrodinger equation:

$$\{\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \exp(ipx)\} / W(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((4))$$

One might argue that kinetic energy is simply an average, but this average is added to $V(x)$ which has physical meaning and so kinetic energy should have physical meaning as well, in some sense. Furthermore, E_n has physical meaning because $E_{n+j} - E_n$, the energy difference between levels $n+j$ and n is associated with the energy of a photon which may be absorbed or emitted. This then seems to be the climbing or descending of the potential hill.

Thus both distinctly different types of interactions are present and one might expect different entropies to be present as well.

For the impulse-space picture, $W(x)W(x)$ yields a spatial probability and $a(p)a(p)$ a momentum one. Each may be used in a Shannon's entropy expression $-\sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$ where $P(i)$ is probability. We suggest one may add the two. This entropy is a consequence of the $\exp(ipx)$ s, no value and $V(x)$ used as these are associated with the physical interactions which occur. These physical interactions also give rise to an average energy of E_n .

The average energy E_n may be associated with different interactions, namely interactions with photons as an example. This is an example of an energy type of interaction. $\exp(-E_n t)$ may be associated with its own entropy based on using $C |\cos(Et)|$ as a probability or $C |\cos(E/c ct)|$ if one wishes to use the variable ct , we suggest.

We note that even though the impulse picture and time one represent different entropies, the former creates the E_n state and so has an influence on it. Furthermore an absorbed photon must lead to a stable resonance state E_{n+j} which is again determined by the impulse picture. Thus the two pictures are not independent.

Time Dependent Wavefunction

One may have a more general time dependent entropy if one uses the time dependent wavefunction:

$$W(x,t) = \sum_n \exp(-iE_n t) b_n W_n(x) \quad ((5)) \quad \text{where } b_n \text{ are constants}$$

In such a case, at each t_i treated as a constant, $W(x,t_i)$ may be used to generate the probabilities $P(x) = W^*(x,t_i)W(x,t_i)$ and $P(p) = a^*(p)a(p)$ using $W(x,t_i) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. One may create Shannon's entropies associated with impulses and add them. There is, however, also a time entropy given by the probability: $W^*(t,x_0)W(t,x_0)$ where x_0 is a fixed point. This is due to fluctuations associated with the various $\exp(-iE_n t)$ in addition to some physical mechanism which allows the particle to jump from one energy state to another.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the classical mechanical concepts of work = change of kinetic energy and impulse = change in momentum vector represent physically different interactions. For example, $p = m_1 v_1 = m_2 v_2$ yield the same impulse, but these two particles do not move up the same height on a potential hill. They are the same for one interaction and not for another. Furthermore, there is an information issue because p does not require the knowledge of m or v ,

only their product, while kinetic energy requires p and m . Two particles with the same kinetic energy which move up a potential hill to the same height, may have different impulses. Thus, it seems, one needs both E and p to describe interactions. The special relativistic vector (p, E) allows for this.

In quantum mechanics, a free particle is represented by the special two dimensional probability (wavefunction) $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. Even if one uses ct instead of t , one has $\exp(-iE/c ct + ipx)$ for a particle with mass. The impulse probability and the energy one (kinetic energy for a free particle) have different frequencies. This leads to different Shannon's entropies if one uses $C1|\cos(Et)|$ or $C2|\cos(px)|$ as probabilities for a single crest. The two, however, represent different physical processes and different information, so it seems two different entropies are justified.

In quantum mechanics, we argue that interactions with $V(x)$ are based on impulses and so use $\exp(ipx)$, i.e. a wavefunction $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$. $V(x)$, however, is an energy and so the energy picture must also be present. One may use the $\exp(ip)$ s to create an average $KE(x)$. This, at first, may seem to be a mathematical process, but if $V(x)$ has physical meaning so should $KE(x)$ as E_{average} is also considered physical. E_{average} is linked with a very different kind of interaction, namely an energy one, i.e. the absorption or emission of photons. There are again two physically distinct interaction processes and we argue that each may have its own entropy.

For a quantum single particle bound state, one may combine impulse interactions with conservation of energy to create a Schrodinger time-independent equation. This yields $W_n(x)=\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ as well as E_n , the average energy. One may create Shannon's entropies using $P(x)=W_n(x)W_n(x)$ and $P(p) = a(p)a(p)$. We suggest adding the two. One also has E_n which is associated with the probability $\exp(-iE_n t)$. This E_n may undergo a different kind of interaction, namely an energy one (absorption or emission of photon), so we suggest a entropy in time based on the probability $C |\cos(E_n t)|$ over a single crest. (One may note that absorption and emission of a photon must lead to a new state which is based on a Schrodinger equation eigenfunction.)

Thus two different entropies (one time-energy based and one largely impulse based) may appear in quantum mechanics, we argue.